

Damage Detection on Wind Turbine Blades

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Abstract—The energy produced by wind turbines is an important source of power because it does not produce toxic gases or contribute to the greenhouse effect. Therefore, it is one of the most efficient and sustainable resources to protect natural resources and maintain an ecological balance. This research focuses on the automation of blade inspection, using different Computer Vision (CV) approaches and methods to detect damage on the wind turbine blades, making use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), and compare a model that best adapts to damage detection solution. To achieve this, different methods, architectures, and deep learning algorithms have been experimented, for Image Classification, Object Detection and Instance Segmentation tasks. An image dataset of wind turbine blade defects, annotated by experts has been used. Different performance metrics were also used to compare and evaluate each model. The experiments were based on a limited dataset, with Classification using Inception_v3[1] reasonable results were obtained, but it is necessary to use image tiles and augmentation methods. In object detection using YOLO_v3[2] also achieved reasonable results even without using image tile methods. For object instance segmentation using Mask R-CNN[3], the results obtained were significantly worse in comparison to the other results obtained. A better-elaborated dataset could considerably improve the results.

Index Terms—[AI, Deep Learning, Damage Detection, Wind Turbine Blades]

1 INTRODUCTION

In a recent study, the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), proclaimed that over the last century, fossil fuels like oil and coal had increased the concentration of atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂). CO₂ in combination with other long-lived gases like Water vapour, Methane, Nitrous oxide and Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) block heat from escaping from the atmosphere, which causes global warming to ensue. Leading causes for the combustion of these fossil fuels are cars, buildings, factories, and power plants which are heavily made use of in today's industry. This is one of the leading reasons why the use of a renewable energy source is so important because it will make the need for these fossil fuels redundant and will prevent the creation of a large part of the CO₂ that is generated[4].

The European Union use of renewable energy sources include wind power, solar power, hydro power, tidal power, geothermal energy, ambient heat captured by heat pumps and biofuels which reached 17.5% in 2017. The goal of the European Union is to reach 20% renewable energy in the year 2020[5]. Wind turbines do not only help prevent the generating of CO₂, also provide the economy with a cheaper alternative to fossil fuels due to the large amounts of electricity which is generated. These wind turbines often require maintenance to be performed on them which is not only quite dangerous for the maintenance workers due to the height and location of the possibly damaged components but also has an associated high cost attached to it.

Fig. 1: Different types of damage on a wind turbine blade

The use of drones with cameras offers a solution to the associated risk of the maintenance work, the high costs of conventional forms of inspection and the slow way of obtaining data. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is defined as the design of an algorithm capable of showing in its behavior the aspect of human intelligence, such as learning and solving problems, in this case with an algorithm to automate the defect detection on the drone made images. In our case, this implies damages on wind turbine blades. We will focus on defect detection and classification, analyzing images of wind turbine blades that have been annotated by domain experts, to determine the status of the blades and find the existence of different types of damage that require attention; an example of possible damages is shown in Fig 1. which are Burst & Cracks(B&C), Erosion and Surface Damage(SD). The main goal of this research is to find a neural network model capable of detecting accurately the different types of damage that can be found on the wind turbine blade. To do this, various performance metrics will be used to evaluate and compare results. Besides, we will use different methods and architectures to find a solution.

1.1 State of the art

In the previous research [6], based on locating damage using a single-state deep network YOLO_v3[2] for object detection task. According to the author, the results were good but only for multi-class detection, not being useful for binary detection. However, it was not possible to reproduce his results. The critical obstacle in this project was the dataset, there were not enough images and classes were unbalanced.

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1.2 Research Questions

In our research, we will working on multiclass detection using three neural networks and different image processing methods to answer the following questions:

- Which neural network would be most suited to detect damages on wind turbine blades?
- How accurate and robust is the neural network?

In this research, we will experiment with image classification using Inception_v3[1], object instance segmentation using Mask R-CNN[3] and object detection using YOLO_v3[2]. An alternative will also be proposed for dataset processing.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section describes the materials and methods used, like necessary software, image process techniques, different neural networks, and different performance metrics for the experiments.

2.1 Dataset

This subsection describes the items that compose the dataset, which contain images and annotations.

2.1.1 Images

Fig. 2: Examples of dataset images

Image datasets	Amount	Resolution
Set 1	35	4032x2268
Set 2	41	3968x2976
Set 3	112	7360x4912

Table 1: Datasets for damage detection on wind turbine blades

The three datasets are shown in Table 1, which contains a total of 188 images. Two examples are shown in Fig 2. On the left is an image with Surface damage and on the right is an image with Erosion. All images are used together for every experiment. The images are in JPEG format. The dataset is split into 80% for training/validation and 20% for testing not used for training and evaluation.

2.1.2 Annotations

Damage type	Annotations	Total percentage
Erosion	62	16.8 %
Surface Damage	272	73.9 %
B&C	19	5.2 %
Dirt	15	4.1%

Table 2: Total annotations for each class

The images have been annotated by a domain experts on wind turbines, using the LabelImg tool[7]. The different types of damage were annotated, these types are Erosion, Burst and Crack (B&C), Dirt and Surface Damage (SD). The specific amounts can be found in Table 2. There is an XML (Extensible Markup Language) file for each image that contains all the objects present in the image. Each file stores the position, height, width and class type of every object present in the image.

2.2 Pre-processing dataset

In this subsection we present four different methods used for dataset processing.

2.2.1 Consecutive tiles

Fig. 3: Frame of consecutive tiles

The goal of consecutive tiles is to produce images with input size compatible with the neural networks that we use. To avoid losing pixels of the image, because the images are large and do not have the same size. Using consecutive tiles ensures that all input images have the same dimension. In our experiments, we use tiles with the same width and height. If the image width and height are not divisible by the tile size, an area at the border of the image is considered out of bounds, this part of the image is discarded. The consecutive tile method is to obtain multiple images from a single image, and separate each of these tiles according to the annotation, as shown in Fig 3. Tiles with two different annotations are considered as multiple damages.

Fig. 4: Example of a tiled image

For example, in the tiling process shown in Fig 4, at tile six, there is a Surface Damage annotation, this tile would be considered as Surface Damage class. The annotation threshold is also introduced for tiles with a percentage of annotation, below this threshold tiles are considered as small damages. Different annotation threshold values will be experimented with. An example is illustrated in Fig 4 at tile 3. This tile does not contain any damage but does contain an annotation because bounding boxes are larger than the actual damage. The annotation threshold used for this example is 5%, and the percentage of annotations in this tile is less than 1%. Since the percentage of the

annotation is smaller than the annotation threshold value, this tile is considered as small damage. At the end of the tiling process, we will have seven classes for our dataset: small damages, multiple damages and no damage, besides the damage types shown in Table 2. The small damage class is not used in any training, evaluation or testing.

2.2.2 Image overlap tiles

Fig. 5: Frame of image overlap tiles

After consecutive tiling, annotations can be split over multiple tiles. This makes it harder for the network to learn this type of damage. Image overlap tile is based on the consecutive tile method, and is used to make sure that the network gets a better tile with annotation inside. This is illustrated in Fig 5. In this example, tiles with the same width and height are made, at coordinates (X_{min}, Y_{min}) to (X_{max}, Y_{max}) , and next tile is at coordinates $(X_{max}-\theta, Y_{min})$ to (X_{max}, Y_{max}) of the next tile which is overlapped with first tile. The θ value is calculated by using the formula: $\theta = \frac{W \cdot \sigma}{100}$ where w is the width of the tile and σ is the overlap percentage.

2.2.3 Image overlap tiles & border check

In the dataset, there are pictures with small annotation, in contrast to consecutive tiles and overlap tiles. In this method, we solve cases where a complete annotation gets found in a single tile, despite which annotation threshold is used to classify small damages. The annotation threshold only applies for annotations bordering the tile, and if an annotation is not bordering the tile, those tiles get sorted according to its annotation.

2.2.4 Image augmentation

(a) Non augmented image. (b) Augmented image.

Fig. 6: Comparison of an augmented and non-augmented image

Due to the unbalanced dataset and the lack of image samples, the dataset is augmented. The augmentation is performed using horizontal and vertical flip movements and different brightness settings. This way a balanced dataset for each class is obtained. Image augmentation is one of the best-known techniques to improve results when the dataset is unbalanced and does not have enough images[8]. In Figure 6, it is shown the comparison of an original image tile and an augmented one. It has been flipped and also its brightness is different.

2.3 Neural networks

During this research, we used three different neural networks for classification, detection and instance segmentation tasks.

2.3.1 Classification

We used the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) Inception_v3[1]¹ it is an image classification model and it is made up of symmetric and asymmetric building blocks, including convolutions, average pooling, max pooling, concats, dropouts, and fully connected layers. Batch-normal is used extensively throughout the model and applied to activation inputs. The default input image size for the Inception_v3[1] model is 299x299.

Fig. 7: Inception_v3[1] architecture[9]

Inception_v3[1] architecture Figure. 7, reuses original ideas from GoogLeNet[10] and VGGNet[11] using large filters more efficiently by using multiple smaller convolutions. Also, the smaller convolutions are asymmetric with different filters to increase performance. The improvements made with Inception_v3[1] are the regularization of the network with batch normalization and label-smoothing. When Inception_v3[1] is used in object detection framework, they could perform well as classifying small and low-resolution objects.

2.3.2 Object detection

The implementation of YOLO_v3[2]² (You only look once), which is a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) that prioritize object detection. YOLO_v3[2] uses Darknet53[12] backbone with a custom convolutional filter, which uses global average pooling to make predictions and uses a 3x3 filter. The filters to extract functions and 1x1 filter to reduce the output of the channels. Eventually, it uses three 3x3 Convolutionary layers, each with a 3x3 output of 1024 output channels. A final 1x1 Convolution layer is then applied to convert a 7x7x7x1026 output to 7x7x125. The default input image size for the YOLO_v3[2] model is 416x416.

¹Inception_v3 implementation can be found here: <https://github.com/EN10/TensorFlowForPoets>

²YOLO.v3 implementation can be found here: <https://github.com/qwweee/keras-yolo3>

Fig. 8: Prediction process in YOLO_v3[2]

YOLO_v3[2] prediction process shown in Fig.8 is a method used to predict the object inside of an image. YOLO_v3[2] divides the image into $S \times S$ grid, each grid cell has only one object as there prediction. Each grid predicts a fixed number of bounding boxes, each with their own confidence score, after it will predict class probability in each grid and create a bounding box around high confident score objects

2.3.3 Object instance segmentation

The implementation of Mask R-CNN[3]³ for the object instance segmentation, which uses deep learning libraries Keras and TensorFlow. Mask R-CNN[3] is a deep neural network aimed to solve instance segmentation problems in machine learning or computer vision.

Fig. 9: FPN lateral connection[13]

This framework is an extension of the Faster R-CNN[14] and is based on Feature Pyramid Network[15] (FPN). Within Fig. 9. FPN lateral connection is shown how it combines low-resolution, semantically strong features with high-resolution and this pyramid has a rich semantics at all levels and is build quickly from a single input image scale.

Fig. 10: Architecture of instance segmentation[16]

³Mask R-CNN implementation can be found here: https://github.com/matterport/Mask_RCNN

Mask R-CNN[3] uses ResNet101[17] backbone, is a standard convolution neural network that serves as a feature extractor. The early layers detect low level features (edges and corners), and later layers successively detect higher level features (car, person, sky). Passing through the backbone network, the image is converted from 1024x1024x3 (RGB) to a feature map of shape 32x32x2048. This feature map becomes the input for the following stages.

Fully Convolutional Network (FCN)[18] is an algorithm for doing semantic segmentation. This model uses various blocks of convolution and max pool layers to first decompress an image to 1/32th of its original size. Mask R-CNN[3] uses up-sampling and deconvolution layers to resize the image to its original dimensions. Identify each object instance of each pixel for every known object within an image which is called instance segmentation, illustrated in Fig. 10.

2.4 Performance metrics

We have used different performance metrics to evaluate and compare the different neural network models used.

2.4.1 Accuracy

Accuracy is used in classification problems, and it is a common evaluation metric. It is defined as the ratio of the number of correct predictions made by the model overall kind of predictions made. It can be seen in Equation 1.

$$accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (1)$$

2.4.2 Intersection over Union (IoU)

IoU is an evaluation metric used to measure the accuracy based on Jaccard Index [19] that evaluates the overlap between two bounding boxes. It requires a ground truth bounding box and a predicted bounding box. IoU is given by Equation 2 IoU formula, the overlapping area between the predicted bounding box and the ground truth bounding box divided by the area of union between them.

$$IoU = \frac{B_p \cap B_{gt}}{B_p \cup B_{gt}} \quad (2)$$

2.4.3 Precision

Precision is defined as the number of TP (true positives) divided by the number of TP plus the number of FP (false positives), shown in Equation 3 Precision formula. Using this formula, we can know what proportion of predictions which are predicted as positives that are actual positives to the total predicted positives.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (3)$$

2.4.4 Recall

Recall is the ability of a model to find all the relevant cases (ground truth bounding boxes). It is the percentage of true positive detected among ground truths and is given by Equation 4 Recall formula.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (4)$$

2.4.5 F1 score

F1 score combines precision and recall relative to a specific positive class, is calculated using Equation 5 F1 score formula. F1 score conveys the balance between the precision and the recall, and there is an uneven class distribution. F1 score reaches its best value at one and worst at zero.

$$F1 = 2 \cdot \frac{precision \cdot recall}{precision + recall} \quad (5)$$

2.4.6 Mean Average Precision (mAP)

The Mean Average Precision is the summation of the Average Precision(AP) of each class divided by the number of classes. It is calculated using Equation 6 mean Average Precision (mAP) formula[20]. The formula tells us is that we calculate for a certain number of corresponding AP and that the average of all these AP scores would then give us a single number, the mAP.

$$mAP = \frac{\text{NumberOfAP} * AP}{\text{NumberOfAP}} \quad (6)$$

2.5 Software and hardware

This sections describes the hardware specifications and the different software packages used during our experiments.

2.5.1 Software

All programming was done in Python, using different packages. An overview of the principal Python packages is listed in Table 3.

Libraries	Version
tensorflow-gpu	1.12.0
keras	2.2.4
matplotlib	3.0.3
numpy	1.16.2
opencv	4.0.0.21
pandas	0.23.4
scipy	1.2.1

Table 3: Libraries specifications

2.5.2 Hardware

The computer used for most of the experiments is "Romke", specifications are shown in Table 4.

Server "Romke"	Hardware	Specifications
CPU	Intel Core i9-7960x	2.9 Ghz
GPU	Geforce RTX 2070	8 GB GDDR6
RAM	Corsair	64 GB

Table 4: Hardware specifications

3 EXPERIMENTS, RESULTS & DISCUSSION

This section will describe the experiments performed, and what materials or methods have been used to perform. It also provides details and discussion for the results achieved in the experiments.

3.1 Image Classification and Tiles

In this experiment, we used Inception_v3[1], we have processed the dataset to generate tiles using consecutive tiles, overlap tiles and overlap tiles & border check methods described in the last section. The dataset mentioned in Table 1 was used for the tiling process. We discard the multi damage class because we are interested in the strongest prediction in each tile, just considering the dominant damage and also because in classification we do not obtain the location of coordinates of the damage but for comparison, the third experiment uses multi damage class. In all the experiments performed in classification, 4000 epochs were used and learning rate of 0.01. We present the classification experiments using the three methods of image tiles, non-augmented and augmented.

3.1.1 Non-augmented damage classification

The experiments were performed using the dataset obtained from using the consecutive tiles, overlap tiles and overlap & border check methods. All the datasets obtained were not augmented. A annotation threshold of 5% for categorizing a tile as containing damage was used, and the overlap threshold between tiles was 25%.

Method	Tile size	Overlap	Accuracy
Consecutive tiles	1500x1500	NO	72%
	299X299	NO	80%
Overlap tiles	1500X1500	25	80%
	299x299	25	78%
Overlap tiles & border check	1500X1500	25	84%
	299x299	25	77%

Table 5: Classification results using Inception_v3[1] and a non-augmented dataset

Results Non-augmented damage classification The results for the three methods used in a non-augmented dataset are shown in Table 5. The accuracy of 84% was achieved using tiles size of 1500x1500. However, the accuracy obtained using neural network input size tiles 299x299 was 80%. Fig 11 shows some examples of predictions.

(a) Predicted Dirt tile and confidence score (b) Predicted SD tile and confidence score

Fig. 11: Predictions for non augmented dataset using inception_v3[1]

3.1.2 Augmented damage classification

In this experiment, we have proceeded to augment the dataset. We have used different techniques to augment the dataset, flipping horizontally and vertically and changing the brightness. Also, different threshold and overlap values were used.

Method	Tile size	Annotation	Overlap	Accuracy
Consecutive tiles	1500x1500	5	NO	81%
	299X299	50	NO	80%
Overlap tiles	1500X1500	5	25	82%
	299x299	50	25	74%
Overlap tiles & border check	1500X1500	5	25	87%
	1500x1500	25	50	96%
	299x299	80	50	91%

Table 6: Classification results using Inception_v3[1] and an augmented dataset

Results Augmented damage classification The results are improved by nearly 10% using augmented consecutive tiles, increasing from 72% to 81% accuracy. However, using augmented overlap tiles & border check only improved the accuracy by 3 %, increasing from 84% to 87% accuracy. Using a higher annotation threshold of 25% and overlap threshold of 50%, it is possible to get a higher accuracy up to 96%. In the results presented, we emphasize that the multiple damages and small damages class were not used.

3.1.3 damage classification with multi damage class

In this experiment, we have proceeded to use the augment and the non-augmented dataset. We have used the same methods, annotation and overlap threshold from the previous experiments to duplicate the results but added the multi damage class.

Method	Tile size	Threshold	Overlap	Accuracy
Consecutive tiles	1500x1500	5	NO	85%
	299x299	50	NO	76%
Overlap tiles	1500x1500	5	25	87%
	299x299	50	25	77%
Overlap tiles & border check	1500x1500	5	25	81%
	299x299	50	25	79%

Table 7: Classification results using Inception_v3[1] and a non-augmented dataset with the multi damage class

Method	Tile size	Threshold	Overlap	Accuracy
Consecutive tiles	1500x1500	5	NO	91%
	299x299	50	NO	83%
Overlap tiles	1500x1500	5	25	88%
	299x299	50	25	87%
Overlap tiles & border check	1500x1500	5	25	91%
	1500x1500	25	50	96%
	299x299	80	50	92%

Table 8: Classification results using Inception_v3[1] and an augmented dataset with the multi damage class

Results damage classification with multi damage class

The best result from non-augmented improved from 84% to 87% with the multi damage class. The best result from augmented stayed on 96% with the multi damage class. In the results shown in Table 7 and 8 it clear to see that multi damage class mostly improved the results for augmented and non-augmented

3.1.4 Discussion damage classification

The best accuracy in the non-augmented dataset was found with overlap tiles & border check. We have achieved up to 84% accuracy. However results obtained using neural network input size tiles (299x299), did not improve relative to image tile versions. Because tiles are small compared to large annotations. Tiles are classified as damaged when there is no real damage, just the annotation that exceeds tiles. This suggests that more accurate annotations are needed.

The augmentation was good practice since it improves the results notably regarding the training with the non-augmented dataset. Another characteristic that influences the results is the threshold used to classify damages into a small class, and the tile overlap threshold. Increasing the damage threshold, we ensure that the tiles have a higher percentage of annotation in it. In other words, each tile has visible damage. Also increasing the tile overlap threshold, we achieve more centred damages. For this reason, it is possible to get up to 96% of accuracy in training for classification, being the highest value reached.

The experiment with multi damage class is an overall improvement of the past two experiments with classification. The best result which is augmented dataset using the method overlap tiles & border check is still the best result with 96%.

3.2 Object detection

We used the deep learning framework YOLO_v3[2] to detect damage in images provided by the experts. We present three experiments performed, using object detection to determine if YOLO_v3[2] could give better results, in terms of accuracy in detection. In all of the object detection experiments with YOLO_v3[2], we train using 100 epochs with a batch size of four because higher batch size cannot be performed on the current hardware shown in Table 4, with a learning rate of 0.001.

Fig. 12: Consecutive tiles with 1000x1000 resolution

3.2.1 Object detection entire images

In this experiment, we proceed to train our model to detect damages using entire images. Image tile methods were not used. However, augmentation was used mentioned in the previous section.

Tiles	mAP	Tau	Precision	Recall	F1
NO	66.36%	0.39	0.85	0.8	0.82

Table 9: Object detection results using YOLO_v3[2]

Results Object detection entire images The result in Table 9 obtained from the first experiment is that the damage can be found inside the image but not the exact location. For 82% of the test images, the damage was found, and the mean average precision was 66% within the annotations.

3.2.2 Object detection consecutive tiles

In the second experiment, we proceed to tile images for training our model to detect damage on the tiles. It will not use the class No damage because there are no annotations inside of the tile. The reconstructed image from tiles shown in Fig 12 has a yellow line made by an expert, each tile has a red line as new annotation within the tile, and the blue line is the YOLO_v3[2] prediction.

Tiles	mAP	Tau	Precision	Recall	F1
1000x1000	80.41%	0.31	0.81	0.79	0.8
608x608	16.37%	0.21	0.59	0.37	0.46
416x416	34.97%	0.56	0.58	0.57	0.57
208x208	20.41%	0.41	0.4	0.44	0.42

Table 10: Object detection results using YOLO_v3[2] with consecutive tiles

Results Object detection consecutive tiles The result in Table 10, obtained from the second experiment is that consecutive tiles improved the results to 80% and the results with smaller images were 34%, 20% and 16%.

3.2.3 Object detection with overlap tiles & border check

The third experiment uses the same settings for training as the second experiment with as changing the modified tile method overlap tiles & border check. The experiments use different overlap thresholds and annotation thresholds.

Tiles	Threshold	Overlap	mAP	Tau	F1
1000x1000	5	25	42.11%	0.42	0.7
608x608	5	25	45.52%	0.5	0.5
608x608	20	25	55.16%	0.42	0.79
416x416	5	25	52.04%	0.1	0.77
416x416	20	25	73.03%	0.35	0.78
416x416	50	50	67.03%	0.5	0.88

Table 11: Object detection results using YOLO_v3[2] with overlap tiles

Tiles	Threshold	Overlap	B&C	SD	Erosion	Dirt
1000x1000	5	25	79%	33%	57%	0%
608x608	5	25	62%	50%	59%	11%
608x608	20	25	79%	66%	75%	0%
416x416	5	25	77%	50%	68%	0%
416x416	20	25	75%	67%	75%	75%
416x416	50	50	92%	89%	87%	0%

Table 12: Results from YOLO_v3[2] overlap tiles per class

Results Object detection with overlap tiles & border check

The result in Tables 11 and 12 obtained from the third experiment is that improving tiles has yielded a result of 88% in the detection of annotations. The mean average precision comes to 67%.

3.2.4 Discussion Object detection

The results from YOLO_v3[2] led to discussion how much of annotation must be inside of the tile to be seen as damage, and how much of a tile may overlap with the previous tile. In experiment two, consecutive tiles improved the results but only with large tiles and the results were worse with small tiles. Most likely because of tiles splitting annotations, which makes it more challenging to train. In experiment three, the class dirt lowered the mean average precision to 67% this is because of the small dataset, we need a better dataset with more samples. For example, dirt is detected as another class that is shown in Fig 13.

Fig. 13: Example of Dirt prediction

3.3 Object instance segmentation

We have used the deep learning framework Mask R-CNN[3] to detect and segment damage using different images made by experts.

3.3.1 Object instance segmentation entire images

In this experiment, we proceed to train a model that can detect and segment the four types of damage annotated: Erosion, SD, B&C, and Dirt. We used 100 epochs for training, which means an iteration over all training data.

Fig. 14: Entire images detection and segmentation using Mask R-CNN[3]

Results Object instance segmentation entire images

It was not possible to obtain results based on segmentation, but some predictions were obtained, in the Fig 14 is shown an example. However, an mAP of 36% was obtained but only based on object detection.

3.3.2 Discussion Object instance segmentation

It was not possible to obtain results because no polygon shape annotations were provided. In order to obtain some results, a polygon mask was created around the rectangle annotations. The mask that has been predicted is practically inaccurate because there is no real mask in training. It is important to emphasize that it is necessary to have polygon shape in the annotations to make correct use of segmentation.

3.3.3 Discussion detection and segmentation

In Table 9, is shown the object detection result using YOLO_v3[2] and entire images. The best performance was an mAP of 80%. The experiment also performed with Mask R-CNN[3] using entire images got an mAP of 36%. Mask R-CNN[3] did not get good results in detection because the segmentation was not successful. Many predictions of segmentation were discarded and only from those that were not, we obtained object detection results.

4 CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

This section contains a summary of the most important findings obtained during the previous sections, complemented by proposals for future work to improve the results and find a better solution.

4.1 Conclusion

The main conclusion is that the dataset is too small, is not annotated accurately, and also different classes annotated are unbalanced. In this research project, we have presented three different neural network implementations and various image processing methods like tiles and augmented images to answer the research questions.

Classification Inception_v3[1], an image recognition model that has been found to better higher accuracy. Overlap tiles & border check and augmentation methods have been a significant contributor to have better results, reaching 96% of accuracy in its best performance. We also emphasize that small damage class were discarded from our experiments.

Object detection YOLO_v3[2], offers an alternative by discarding segmentation and making use of detection only with bounding boxes. The best result came from object detection, and overlap tiles & border check with an F1 of 0.88 and the best mAP of 80% came from consecutive tiles. While the results found using Mask R-CNN is lower just reached 36% of mAP.

Object instance segmentation Mask R-CNN[3], a two-state framework to detect and segment damage. The experiment was not successful due to annotations shape, to use segmentation accurately annotations have to been annotated as polygonal shape around the item of interest.

Which neural network would be most suited to detect damage on wind turbine blade?

In this project Inception_v3[1] performed better than other proposed neural networks, but to emphasize classification only has an idea that the item of interest is positioned inside of an image and that multiple damage classification is not used.

How accurate is the neural network?

Inception_v3[1] achieved an accuracy of 96%, but it is necessary to use the overlap tiles & border check and augmentation methods.

4.2 Future Work

The use of segmentation could be a good approach, but it is necessary to use polygon shape annotations to make the correct use of segmentation. Adequate annotations could lead to better results.

YOLO_v3[2] obtains reasonable results but has difficulty distinguishing damage, and this is due to the lack of images of the dataset for example dirt in Fig 13. It could be remedied by identifying the classes, and Surface Damage can be distinguished into multiple classes based on the appearance of the Surface Damage.

In the classification task, we only used Inception_v3[1]. Experimenting with different neural network models could be a good approach to finding a better solution. It is also interesting to continue with the tile approach, can be experimented with a new dataset. In addition a new version of the tiles created from the central point of the annotation using a threshold could give better results.

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